

STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF PEPTONES. PART III

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Absorption of formaldehyde by different brands of peptones has been studied. From the absorption curves similarity in composition can be inferred among some of them.

It is known that a protein molecule reacts with formaldehyde and the linkage takes place mainly at groups other than the peptide chain (-CONH-). The formaldehyde might react with one or other reacting groups that may remain free in any particular protein or its hydrolysed products. As such a study on the mode of such reactions and absorption might offer a clue to the nature of the union of the various amino-acids that build up a protein molecule and thereby a differentiation may be made between proteins of apparently same nature. In this paper certain observations on the behaviour of formaldehyde with certain animal proteins and some varieties of commercial peptones have been made.

EXPERIMENTAL

Different proteins as well as different varieties of commercial peptones were taken for experiment. In the case of protein 5 g. of the sample (fat-free and well minced) were taken in a stoppered phial, 50 c.c. dipotassium hydrogen phosphate solution (0.05 M) were added. Formaldehyde solution (8.5%), previously neutralised to pH 7.0, was added in volumes of 1 c.c., 2 c.c. 3 c.c. and 4 c.c. and the final volume was made up to 100 c.c. with K_2HPO_4 (0.05 M) solution. Amount of moisture present in the sample was taken into account when diluting the volume to 100 c.c. In the case of peptone 1 g. was dissolved in K_2HPO_4 solution (0.05 M), formaldehyde was added in different concentrations and the final volume was made up to 100 c.c. with K_2HPO_4 solution.

In each case a few c.c. of toluene were added and the whole was incubated at 30° for 24 hours. Moisture was determined by keeping the substance at 105° till the weight became constant. After 24 hours, free formaldehyde was estimated by dimedone reagent according to the method of Wordsworth and Pangborn (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, I, 116). The dimedone-formaldehyde compound was always purified by acetone, filtered in a gooch crucible, dried at 110-120° for 2 hours and weighed. Formaldehyde was calculated by using the factor 0.1027 per mg. of the compound and by difference formaldehyde absorbed was determined. Moreover, Witte peptone and Bacto-peptone were separately hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid (6 N), the acid was practically removed in vacuum and then neutralised. A 1% solution was made with K_2HPO_4 solution (0.05 M) and treated with different concentration of formaldehyde as usual. The weight of formaldehyde (in g.) absorbed per g. of the different nitrogenous materials in 24 hours at 30° is shown in Table I; the graph indicates the logarithm of the formaldehyde concentration per litre against that of the formaldehyde adsorbed per g. of the protein or the peptone material.

TABLE I

Conc. HCHO (g./litre).	g. of HCHO absorbed per g. of substance			
	0.85	1.7	3.4	6.8
(1) Witte peptone	0.0258	0.0325	0.0426	0.0604
(2) ,, (hydrolysed)	0.0342	0.0531	0.1070	—
(3) Bacto-peptone	0.0234	0.0385	0.0385	0.0385
(4) ,, (hydrolysed)	0.0394	0.0850	0.1100	0.1227
(5) Armour peptone	0.0190	0.0232	0.0326	0.0392
(6) Beef	0.0149	0.0259	0.0306	0.0309
(7) Pork	0.0073	0.0124	0.0200	0.0241

From the experiment so far carried out with the absorption of formaldehyde with different

Bacto-peptone). From the curves, the existence of a similarity may be inferred in beef and bacto-peptone, whereas a similarity exists amongst Witte peptone and Armour peptone.

proteins and peptones it appears that some of them are similar in nature (*vide graph*). Since the absorption of formaldehyde by protein or its breakdown products such as peptones depends on the arrangement of different polar groups in the molecule, it may be taken that absorption curves of proteins with similar group arrangement in the molecule will run parallel and those for protein of different arrangement will cut each other (*cf.* Bacto-peptone and Witte peptone, both hydrolysed and non-hydrolysed). In the breakdown products of proteins, the results are as might be expected. The process of hydrolysis by acids or enzymes opens up new groups by fission, there is a greater absorption of formaldehyde and the absorption curves run parallel; only the degree of absorption varies (*cf.* Witte peptone and

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